

AN ANALYSIS OF EDUCATORS' EXPRESSIONS TO THE LEARNING PROGRAMMES

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study report is to determine how trainees respond to the Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan's training curriculum. The study identifies the aspects that highlight the trainees' favourable reactions, as well as the variables that influence those dimensions. A standardised questionnaire from the lecturers was used to collect feedback from the learners on the training programme. To develop the factor that determines the trainee's reaction, the statistical tool employed was factor analysis. The trainer, the training method, and the information provided by the trainer during the programme were identified as three components through factor analysis. According to the findings, trainees have a good attitude toward the trainer, and the component impacting the trainees' attitude is the trainer's clarity regarding concept and content.

Keywords: Evaluation, Educators, Precision, Education

INTRODUCTION

Any organization's success is determined by the talents and skills of its employees, which are determined by the employee's ability to complete the training that the organisation provides. Training and development has received greater attention in recent years, and it has become a standard activity practised by all businesses and institutions, as it contributes to the attainment of organisational goals.

Nearly 86 percent of respondents said they use level 1 evaluation (the trainees' reaction to training) to assess the effectiveness of a training programme. 2011 (Attia, Honeycutt, & Rana) "How learners see and feel about a certain training module or programme is called reaction. In many organisations, response is the primary or only method of evaluating training because it is a cost-effective and time-efficient method.

To measure the effectiveness of a training programme, about 86 percent of respondents claimed they employ level 1 evaluation (the trainees' reaction to training). "How learners see and feel about a particular training module or programme is called response," according to Attia, Honeycutt, and Rana (2011). Because it is a cost-effective and time-efficient strategy, many organisations employ response as the major or only means of evaluating training.

The Indian government, which has committed and continues to invest a significant amount of money in teacher development through in-service programmes, must evaluate how effective these programmes are over time. Only through analysing the efficiency of a training programme can its success be evaluated. Analyzing the teachers' reactions yields reaction outcomes that assess perception, emotion, and a subjective appraisal of the training programmes, since a positive reaction motivates instructors to study and defines their level of satisfaction with the training programme. As a result, it is critical to examine the teachers' reactions to the training programme, which is crucial in determining how effective the training programmes have been, as well as acquiring and utilising information to enhance the overall quality of the programme for future usage.

LITERATURE OF REVIEW

Kirkpatrick proposed a four-level system for assessing the effectiveness of a training programme in his article. The learners' reactions to the training programme and the instructor are identified at the response level. The learners' experiences and responses to the training programme are assessed. The goal of assessing trainee reaction is to improve the training program's quality. (2015, Khasawneh & Al-Zawahreh) The focus of the study was to determine how students reacted to a career-related training programme. The experiment was carried out using Morgan and Casper's apparatus (2000).

Apart from the fact that employees in a supportive organisational climate are more likely to learn and apply the knowledge and skills acquired during training, people with low self-efficacy are less likely to open new situations and are less able to cope with demands and manage their own situations, compared to people with high efficacy, who will have a positive attitude toward training. Finally, the researcher came to the conclusion that the trainees' knowledge of the training program's reputation, rather than the other variables, influenced their behaviour.

The efficacy of a training programme is determined by the degree to which the training outcome fits the objectives. Only by designing a training programme to satisfy the needs of all students and treating them equally and equitably can a training programme be effective. The effectiveness of the trainees varies depending on their age, gender, and job title. Long and Lori (2005) investigated the association between pre-training motivation and trainee responsiveness to on-line training. A substantial association was discovered between the trainees' reaction and the learning outcomes when the trainees' or learners' control over the training programme was increased. Conversely, learner satisfaction with the teacher influences total training programme satisfaction. The research also revealed that the reaction attitude does not exist before to training because it is formed throughout the training process. As a result, the study concluded that pre-training motivation and trainee effort have a moderate association.

(1995) Warr and Bunce The post-training reaction was discovered as being of three types expressed delight, usefulness, and difficulty in a research undertaken to assess trainees' attitude to the programme. Because the relevance of a training programme is a greater opportunity to transfer it to the work environment, the extent to which trainees enjoy a training programme is not associated with learning achievement or change in behaviour. Instead, the reaction of perceived usefulness of the training programme is mostly associated with changes in work behaviour. The learner's perceived difficulty is the amount of cognitive and emotional effort necessary; if the content is challenging for the trainee, he or she is less likely to acquire the knowledge or skill. Individuals with stronger self-efficacy appear to appreciate the training programme, whereas those with lower self-efficacy appear to dislike it. (Facteau and colleagues, 1995) The trainee's reaction, or attitude, may be influenced by his or her previous experience with a certain training programme or by the opinions of coworkers who have already finished the training programme. 1984 (Newby & Bramely) The primary goal of evaluating a training programme is to identify learning outcomes, as well as to establish a link between learning, training, and work application and innovation.

Learning why a training programme was held is the most effective way to assess its effectiveness, because if a training objective/course is not clearly stated before a training programme is held, the training programme will not go as planned. Long-term reactions of a trainee, learning effects, and behavioural changes that have occurred as a result of the training course can all be measured through evaluations.

REACTION

To evaluate a training program's reaction, learning, behaviour, and results, the model included four levels. Kirkpatrick, Kirkpatrick, Kirkpatrick, Kirkpatrick, Kirkpatrick, Kirkpatrick, Kirkpatrick, Kirkpatrick, Kirkpatrick, The initial level of reaction collects comments on the learning experience following the training programme. (AlYahya, Mat, and Saad) Information about the trainee's pleasure, level of participation, and the training's relevance.

OBJECTIVES

To investigate the component that has the most impact on the trainees' (educators') responses

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to examine how teachers (trainees) react to several relevant aspects in a training programme; understanding how teachers (trainees) react to those factors provides insight into the trainees' (teachers') satisfaction level and impression of the training programme. The goal of the study is to determine which elements had a significant impact on teachers' reactions, as well as which

factors were ineffective in influencing trainees' positive reactions and why. The study will also look into the aspects that have been overlooked or that have failed to elicit a good response, as well as the reasons behind this, in order to raise awareness for future training and programme development. The research is particularly crucial since it aids in determining how much of what was taught throughout the training programme was transferred. Finally, the study serves as a foundation for determining the current success of the training programme as well as the desired changes and enhancements that must be addressed in the nearish term for the program's effectiveness.

METHODOLOGY

A total sample of 150 teachers was chosen from a population of 100 teachers who had participated in the in-service training programme. A five-point Likert Scale questionnaire was created, along with reverse questions, to determine the teachers' reactions to various reviews, and it was then distributed to the responders. The sample included the following demographics: The remaining 23% had completed teacher training after graduation and the remaining 23% were still in the process of completing teacher training after graduation.

The dimensions of the Trainee Reactions items utilised in this study were: teacher, material, training method, goal, and training facility.

Learner's response: Previous studies provided the items for this component. The dimension included 16 questions about the trainer's understanding of the subjects, teaching and visual aids, communication ability, rapport, attitude, capacity to clear doubts, preferred learning style, and overall rating. A five-point Likert scale was used to rate each item, with 5 indicating excellent and 1 indicating poor. ($=.78$) was the Cronbach alpha value.

Finding

Seventy-four percent of the respondents agreed that the trainer's explanations were clear and that the use of visual and teaching aids was effective. While the rest were deemed outstanding and equitable.

Similarly, 84 percent of candidates agree that the trainer was willing to answer questions and that the trainer's communication skills were excellent. Ninety percent of the trainees thought the trainer's attitude was excellent.

In terms of the trainer's training methods, 94% of the trainees agree that they had the opportunity to interact with other trainers, and 82 percent of the trainees thought appropriate aids were used to deliver the concept, which is important because adult learning is more effective when brain storming, practical application, and group discussion are used.

Seventy-four percent of trainees thought the training content was of high quality, and seventy-two percent thought it was well-organized.

Out of six elements, the reaction to the trainer, training material, and training method, three factors related to training content were identified by factor analysis. As a result, it is clear that the trainee and the training content have a strong link.

CONCLUSION

The trainees' reactions are determined by training content variables such as idea clarity, materials offered, and training methods used in the training programme, according to the trainees' responses. In this training programme, however, context elements such as the physical surroundings and refreshment have little impact on the participants.

Consequently, during the establishment of a training programme for adult learners, the material delivered to the trainees should be of immediate value and relevance, the training presentation interesting, and the trainees having the opportunity to share their experiences. In terms of the training programme, it has been observed that the material provided to the trainees and the ability to speak with other learners has been beneficial.

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